

EOSC WITHIN NATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR DIGITAL SKILLS

RECOMMENDATIONS REPORT

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Abbreviations

AC	Associated Countries
DG CNECT	Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content & Technology
DG EAC	Directorate-General for Education & Culture
DG GROW	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship & SMEs
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research & Innovation
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, Qualifications & Occupation
EU	European Union
ICT	Information & Communications Technology
IT	Information Technology
LLL	Lifelong Learning
QA	Quality Assurance
SRIA	Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities & Threats
TGB	Technopolis Group Belgium

1 Executive Summary

The report is targeting at providing a list for recommendations for various types of policy makers (including EOSC stakeholders) with the purpose of providing well-rounded, all-inclusive (research-government-industry-public) options to include into national strategies for Digital Skills and upskilling. The framework, within which the recommendations were deployed, considered:

- The COVID-19 pandemic and the rapid changes in the digital transformation of key areas, science and research included, revealing the role of data: FAIRness and OPENness, Artificial Intelligence expansion, Data Science, e-infrastructures, e-services, interoperability (technical-human), digital skills for all. This is much more relate to the development of the competent human capital to practice and facilitate EOSC Open Science principles;
- EOSC digital skills ecosystem and the skills’ needs associated to run and use data for research (Researchers, ICT professionals, Libraries & Information Scientists);
- EOSC training infrastructure components: organisation, processes, content, resources (human and technical)
- The key thematic areas (building blocks) for HR development and upskilling: People & Actors, Policies, Governance & Processes, Technology & Learning Environments and their translation into the assessed complexity of the EOSC ecosystem regarding the digital upskilling for researchers:

The analysis has also considered the landscape analysis of 9 EU MS/AC: DN, FI, FR, GR, HU, LT, NL, PT, CH, the resulting GAP Analysis, and an EOSC Consultation for the validation of the gaps and of the initially identified actions to be taken to tackle them.

The **eleven (11) key recommendations** developed on the basis of the previous analysis are presented below:

The above recommendations can also be categorised according to the four key thematic areas: Policies, People and Actors, Governance/Processes, Technology and Infrastructure, as indicated previously:

Finally, for each key recommendation a detailed analysis is provided, comprising references related to: the association of the recommendation to the SRIA Priorities for Skills & Training, the identification of specific action needed for its implementation, the expected outputs, the stakeholders that need to be involved, as well as the shared costs & the potential sources of funding.

2 Background for the Analysis

2.1 Scope of the Report

The report is targeting at providing a list for recommendations for various types of policy makers (including EOSC stakeholders) with the purpose of providing well-rounded, all-inclusive (research-government-industry-public) options to include in national strategies for Digital Skills and upskilling. Recommendations will address the following aspects:

- Human capital development, including digital skills and leadership programmes;
- Cross-sectoral employability and demand driven competences development;
- Learning environments and infrastructure to support upskilling;
- Shared costs and funding structures.

The recommendations have taken into account: the landscape analysis of 9 EU MS/AC: DN, FI, FR, GR, HU, LT, NL, PT, CH, the resulting GAP Analysis, and an EOSC Consultation for the validation of the gaps and of the initially identified actions to be taken.

2.2 EOSC in Digital Skills

With the adoption of the Digital Single Markets strategy on 6 May 2015, the EC announced the launch of a cloud for research data – the ‘research open science cloud’. The ‘European Open Science Cloud’ (EOSC) aims to create a trusted environment for hosting and processing research data to support EU science in its global leading role.

The initiative reinforces Open Science, Open Innovation and Open Policies to the world. It aims to foster best practices of global data findability and accessibility (FAIR data), help researchers get their data skills recognised and rewarded (careers, altmetrics); help address issues of access and copyright (IPR) and data subject privacy; allow easier replicability of results and limit data wastage e.g. of clinical trial data (research integrity); contribute to clarification of the funding model for data generation and preservation, reducing rent-seeking and priming the market for innovative research services.

2.2.1 EOSC Working Group (EOSC WG) on Skills & Training

The **EOSC Working Group (EOSC WG) on Skills & Training** started in January 2020 and included 38 members from 24 countries, representing universities, data centers, libraries, ministries, infrastructures, policy makers as well as education/learning. Experience in both data and ICT is covered by the Members of the WG.

The “Skills and Training” Working Group is working on building competence (skills) and capabilities (training) for EOSC. The goal is to provide a framework for a sustainable training infrastructure to support EOSC in all its phases and ensure its uptake. The WG will consult and converge with existing initiatives and H2020 EOSC projects to agree upon key components for skills development and training, determine how these can be embedded in different levels of EOSC (institutional, national, EU), and identify what structures are needed to make EOSC a viable success (sustainability). Therefore, the EOSC Skills and Training Working Group focuses on:

1. Skills development framework (competences) for organizational culture change and service development
2. EOSC training framework/infrastructure (capabilities), targeting trainers and professional groups that support researchers in the stewardship of research outputs and service providers in providing their services via EOSC

Digital and Open Science Skills are a cornerstone in EOSC's operations and future. Developing and sustaining the skills of researchers, research support staff, and EOSC service providers is essential for the success of the EOSC vision. An EOSC network is actually working to bring a culture change for sharing research outcomes, policy awareness, and compliance and knowledge of ICT support services, as well as to empower individuals and institutions to develop and maintain EOSC competences science and capabilities.

2.2.2 SRIA: Skills Development, Training & Education

To realise its vision of a strong digital research data ecosystem with data and software at its core, EOSC launches a concerted effort in education and training to develop and up-skill its human resources. Key actions for success are:

- Promote 'transparency and recognition of skills and qualifications', as this is particularly relevant to the task of recognising open science skills, and consequently the challenge to provide a framework to validate these skills.
- Foster an equitable and balanced digital research labour market, with equity and inclusiveness regarding geographical (brain circulation), disciplinary, gender, ethnicity and age (early career) aspects.
- Strengthen cross-sector (research-industry-public sector) mobility and employability. Of particular importance are the transferable digital skills additional to data and ICT knowledge, such as communication and leadership. Industry and the public sector are key contributors to digital up-skilling and improved alignment will maximise the benefits of training provided by different sectors.
- Invest in people to ultimately create an ecosystem that promotes learning, experimenting and growth. Facilitate and cultivate a digital and open science culture within research organizations (Research Performing Organizations, funding agencies, academia) for a wide researcher buy-in, by investing and prioritizing training and collaboration tools for researchers.
- Build resilience into digital skills and training, to deal with both the "shock" of a new technology coming to the fore, or in the case of COVID-19, suddenly needing a certain part of the population to increase a type of digital skills³. Design skills and training strategies that proceed at the same speed as technological developments.
- Embed the human/people factor in the design of future digital skills systems from the onset as data intensive science (EOSC will evolve as new technologies and sharing models emerge) to recognise when a step change is coming and work alongside the developing technology to develop training around it.

EOSC has already assessed the gaps to shift the culture of research towards openness and transparency, to build bridges between different organizational models, to approach digital literacy in various modes and settings, while working on existing initiatives and preconditions (. These refer to:

1. Lack of digital core expertise; not enough adequately trained people to meet current demand for open and data intensive science needs, let alone increasing demand, nor is there a concerted effort in skills and capacity development which is a crucial element to build and exploit the full potential of the EOSC;
2. Lack of a clear definition of digital professional profiles; Data scientists, data stewards, data curators and research software engineers are some of the different actors needed for the development of data-driven, data intensive science;
3. Existence of disparities; Although the reliance on the emerging new scholarly data and software support profiles are cornerstone elements in the implementation of FAIR data mandates there is a very diverse and uneven picture across Europe;
4. Lack of expertise: There is not sufficient support to the technological development for "FAIR-by-design";
5. Lack of legal/IPR and data ethics expertise;
6. Lack of interdisciplinarity, coordinated and coherent approaches to skills and competences building and for education and training provision;
7. Fragmentation in training resources; Quality and FAIRness of training and learning resources remains a challenge.

According to the above-mentioned gaps, EOSC will target activities to improve the skills of researchers and other relevant EOSC stakeholders, as well as improve the training offered. An important objective will be for EOSC skills and training to permeate educational curricula and competence centres. The priorities according to which EOSC main target will be achieved comprise:

Priority 1: Developing the next generation of data/EOSC professionals.

Priority 2: Educating students and researchers.

Priority 3: EOSC to become a trusted and long-lasting knowledge hub of learning materials and tooling

Priority 4: Developing an EOSC leadership programme to foster the right policy environment for skills and training.

2.2.3 EOSC Association

The EOSC Association was established on 29 July 2020 as a not-for-profit international association (AISBL), established in Belgium, involving research and innovation stakeholders across the EU and beyond. The Association provides a means recognised by the EC to serve the EOSC community, promote alignment of EOSC contributions at all levels and enable Open Science in Europe.

The Association is the focal point of the EOSC Partnership with the European Commission. It will **continuously develop the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda**, which shall influence future EOSC activities at institutional, national and EU level (including the EOSC-related work programmes in Horizon Europe) and, among others, **coordinate and foster technical environments and promote the skills that enable the federation of existing and new scientific data infrastructures**.

2.3 EOSC Skills & Training SWOT Analysis

European Skills Agenda and Action Plan for Digital Education 2021-2027 in place

European support to open science skills' upgrade

EOSC Establishment and operation

EOSC Association has been founded

EOSC WGs & TFs contributing to a multilevel approach for digital upskilling

FAIR principles established

EC Open Data/ Access strategies formulated- Open Data Directive

Data Strategy/White Paper on Artificial Intelligence pillars of the EC Digital Strategy

Digital Skills & Jobs Coalitions taking action to tackle the lack of digital skills in Europe

Interaction of different research communities/participative approach adopted to tackle the challenges identified

New Funding Instruments for 2021-2027 including RRF have been established and set priority on Digital Transition

Integrated review of all components influencing EOSC principles' adoption to national policies

Human Capital rich in technological skills

Disparity of national approaches targeting digital skills upgrade

Horizontal development of action under the view of 'one size fits all'

Cultural gaps not being addressed

Data environment's rapid changes

Governance complexity in Research-Industry-Public sector schemes not being addressed

Absence of coordination framework for EOSC principles' integration to digital upskilling

Impact of AI on education and training: transformative but also with major risks connected to fundamental rights, as well as ethical, data protection and privacy

Challenges regarding the involvement of end-users, accessibility, inclusion and equity, ethics, data protection and privacy and security

Lack of digital core expertise/Lack of digital skills profiles

Gaps between academia curricula outcomes and market demand

Disparities in academic curricula, training courses, development and operation of learning environments and platforms related to OS digital skills

Researchers' digital upskilling not clearly addressed as a priority in LLL;

Disparities among national priorities and initiatives for digital upskilling and open science

Absence of institutionalisation in developing OS digital upskilling approaches and frameworks

Absence of standalone National Strategies for Digital Skills

Absence of Certification Frameworks for digital skills

Absence of researchers' career development framework related to EOSC principles

Competence Centres not established or operating under a scope related to OS

Weak bonds of cross-sector (research-industry-public sector) mobility and employability

Deficiencies concerning spread awareness on OS principles

Absence of federate data infrastructures

EOSC principles being streamlined to national policies for digital skills and EOSC being the reference point for the development of OS digital upskilling framework

EOSC leadership for fostering the right policy environment for skills and training

Innovation embedded in training content, means and services' delivery

Co-development of digital upscaling training curricula involving different groups of EOSC ecosystem stakeholders

Adoption of the lifecycle-based skills approach for the development of the relevant profiles

PPPs in Open Science

Operation of Digital Competence Centres: establishment of networks at cross-disciplinary and cross-national levels

Establishment and operation of networks of researchers-champions in open science acting as EOSC principles' ambassadors

Future need for digitally competent workforce and a large pool of digital talent with basic and advanced digital skills, including those related to emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, for fostering technology-driven economy and research

Rapid advances in emerging technologies in short cycles, strongly impacting the skills required for data management

Funding for promoting and rewarding OS principles in practice

COVID-19 crisis with likely impact on the level and future demand for digital skills

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2.4 The Concept Framework for EOSC Digital Skills Positioning in National Strategies

2.4.1 The process leading to the recommendations

The study was developed according to the following process:

An initial **Desk Research** on ongoing Digital Skills initiatives in MS/AC, accompanied by an investigation of the digital maturity of each country, its digital competitiveness and future readiness, as well as the effective impact of ICT on society and its development was conducted based on which, a shortlist of 12 countries, covering representative regions of Europe to be further analysed was proposed to the EOSC WG. Following consultations with the EOSC WG, the number countries were reduced to nine (9). Based on a list of experts and reference points provided by the EOSC WG for each selected country, **interviews** were conducted, and **specific country reports** were drafted, including findings from **literature/desk review** as well.

Having completed the mapping of the 9 countries, a comparison was performed, mainly qualitative, to the priorities set by EOSC. The **potential gap** or overlap has indicated whether additional emphasis should be put to the alignment of the national plans. It has also indicated whether suggested common actions were to be considered within the recommendations of EOSC.

Based on the results of the previous tasks and the emerging EOSC SRIA and Partnership documents, an analysis provided insights on how to best position EOSC Skills and Training in Digital Skills in national strategies and agendas. Through a **structured consultation**, insights on the following aspects:

- Data intensive science and open science: role and connection with public and industry sectors;
- Data profiles in research track. Role of university curricula in building profiles/ capacities;
- Role and placement of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme. Special consideration for HPC and AI related competence centers was given;
- Best use of existing human and technical infrastructure (e.g., libraries, data centres)

have been provided. The consultation was accompanied by a **focus group discussion** to validate its outcomes and the resulting draft recommendations.

2.4.2 The framework for the analysis

The framework, within which the recommendations were deployed, has taken into account:

- The COVID-19 pandemic and the rapid changes in the digital transformation of key areas, science and research included, revealing the role of data: FAIRness and OPENess, Artificial Intelligence expansion, Data Science, e-infrastructures, e-services, interoperability (technical-human), digital skills for all. This is much more relate to the development of the competent human capital to practice and facilitate EOSC Open Science principles;
- EOSC digital skills ecosystem:

and the skills needs associated to run and use data for research (Researchers, ICT professionals, Libraries & Information Scientists);

- EOSC training infrastructure components: organisation, processes, content, resources (human and technical)
- The key thematic areas (building blocks) for HR development and upskilling: People & Actors, Policies, Governance & Processes, Technology & Learning Environments and their translation into the assessed complexity of the EOSC ecosystem regarding the digital upskilling for researchers:

2.4.3 How to read the recommendations

The recommendations are presented in the form of a table:

RECOMMENDATION #	Description
	Thematic Area: <i>it involves the related building block chosen among the following: People & Actors, Policies, Governance & Processes, Technology & Infrastructure</i>
Rationale	<i>It relates to the provision of all relevant documentation for supporting the recommendation, as resulting from the gap analysis, the desk research and the consultation results</i>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p><i>It relates to the correlation of the recommendation, and of its suggested action, to the SRIA priorities, as codified by the study team</i></p> <p>1. Developing the next generation of open science and data professionals.</p> <p>1.1 Education on EOSC knowledge fields</p> <p>1.2 Lifelong learning on EOSC knowledge fields and digital skills</p> <p>1.3 Recognition (evaluation and reward mechanisms) of EOSC professionals and researchers</p> <p>1.4 Professional digital career paths development</p> <p>1.5 EOSC professionals' mobility to industry and public domain</p> <p>1.6 Standardization of digital skills profiles</p> <p>1.7 Recognition and accreditation models of digital skills</p>

	<p><i>1.8 Quality assurance framework and certification mechanisms for trainers and trainees to ensure continuous improvement, accountability and sustainability, in alignment to the technology progress and any social or economic emergencies</i></p> <p><i>1.9 Digital competence centers, networks of experts or any other alliances (working on the co-development of common practices and tools, stimulating and promoting the mobility of students, digital professionals and domain experts, and creating mobility opportunities beyond EOSC such as industrial internships).</i></p> <p>2. Coordinating training and aligning curricula for students and researchers.</p> <p><i>2.1 Higher education curriculum on digital skills on EOSC knowledge field aligned with industry demand</i></p> <p><i>2.2 Training of researcher in open science principles</i></p> <p><i>2.3 Lifelong learning and upskilling for citizens and researchers on EOSC knowledge field</i></p> <p><i>2.4 Bridging researchers to industry</i></p> <p><i>2.5 Advanced learning environments on EOSC knowledge fields</i></p> <p><i>2.6 Recognition (evaluation and reward mechanisms) of EOSC researchers</i></p> <p><i>2.7 Networks of researchers and EOSC professionals in open science</i></p> <p><i>2.8 Mobility of researchers</i></p> <p>3. Building a trusted and long-lasting knowledge hub of learning materials and related tools.</p> <p><i>3.1 Quality assurance and certification framework for learning material for lifelong learning, ensuring up to date with technology and policy changes</i></p> <p><i>3.2 Framework for lifelong learning pathways for different data/EOSC profiles</i></p> <p><i>3.3 Training/Educational Repositories on EOSC knowledge filed as part of digital competence centers or universities entities</i></p> <p><i>3.4 Open learning and communication environments/platforms applying open science principles</i></p> <p>4. Developing an EOSC leadership programme to foster the right policy environment for data skills and training.</p> <p><i>4.1 National policies and initiatives on open/data science</i></p> <p><i>4.2 National policies and initiatives on digital skills</i></p> <p><i>4.3 National policies and initiatives on emerging technologies (AI, HPC, Cybersecurity etc)</i></p> <p><i>4.4 Linking universities, research, public domain and industry</i></p>
Suggested Actions	<i>It relates to the proposal of specific action for supporting the implementation of the recommendation</i>
Expected outputs	<i>It relates to the expected outputs as a result of the proposed specific action's implementation</i>
Stakeholders involved	<p><i>It relates to the identified EOSC stakeholders, involved in the implementation of the recommendation:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Policymakers: European Commission, EOSC-EOSC Association, MS/AC governments</i> ▪ <i>Institutions: universities and research performing organisations.</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Research funders: the European Commission, national research funders, and other funders of research activity.</i> ▪ <i>Research communities: practitioners from all research fields, clustered around disciplinary interests, data types or cross-cutting grand challenges.</i> ▪ <i>Industry: Business Associations, SMEs, PPPs</i> ▪ <i>Scientific Libraries, LIBER</i> ▪ <i>Data service providers: repositories, data storage, processing and appropriate sharing service providers</i> ▪ <i>Standards bodies: Competences Agencies, Accreditation Organisations</i> ▪ <i>Publishers: not-for-profit and commercial, Open Access and paywall publishers of research papers and data.</i>
<p>Shared costs & funding</p>	<p><i>It relates to the identification of the relevant financial instruments for the funding of the suggested action</i></p>

3 Recommendations for the positioning of EOSC within National Strategies

3.1 Recommendations at a glance

The recommendations drafted are covering all aspects related to digital upskilling, as reveal by the study and the regarding consultation and aligned to the concept presented in the previous chapter. Eleven (11) key recommendations are revealed as presented below:

They can also be categorised according to four dimensions: Policies, People and Actors, Governance/Processes, Technology and Infrastructure:

3.2 Recommendations' analysis

3.2.1 RECOMMENDATION 1. Integrate measures for digital upskilling in national open science policies, fully respecting the legal, ethical and IPR aspects

RECOMMENDATION 1. Integrate measures for digital upskilling in national open science policies, fully respecting the legal, ethical and IPR aspects	
	Thematic Area: Policy
Rationale	<p>Although the reliance on FAIR and open data seems to be an undisputed challenge towards digital transition and research progress across the European countries, and the demand for skilled labour force in digital data field is continuously increasing, <i>most of the countries studied do not have yet established integral National Open Science and/or Digital Skills Policies</i>. Instead, only piecemeal approaches to digital upskilling on Open/Data Science are in place. Furthermore, it seems that many entities, belonging to the scientific or governmental hierarchy, claim the role and the authority for policy making and monitoring regarding components of Open Science and/or Digital Skills Strategies, even though none of them seems to carry on the full responsibility.</p> <p>According to the Gap Analysis and Landscape Report, there is “<i>no concerted effort in skills and capacity development which is a crucial element to build and exploit the full potential of the EOSC</i>”, while it has been found that in the majority of cases studied there is “<i>lack of interdisciplinarity, coordinated and coherent approaches to skills and competences building and for education and training provision</i>” especially as regards to the open science issues. As a result, a question of fragmentation on governance of Open Science policies arises, especially when it comes to the upskilling issue.</p> <p>Besides, even when some type of national Open Science/Access policy is in place, its broad adoption and endorsement from all the research institutes nationwide is called into question, which may due to the lack of a relevant statutory framework. On European level, there is also a lack of a coherent institutional framework on Open Science that tackles upskilling. In addition, “<i>lack of legal/IPR and data ethics expertise</i>” has been observed since very few countries have approached these issues in their policies.</p>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p>4.1 National policies and initiatives on open/data science</p> <p>4.2 National policies and initiatives on digital skills</p> <p>4.3 National policies and initiatives on emerging technologies (AI, HPC, Cybersecurity etc.)</p>
Suggested Actions to be taken	<p>1. EOSC may develop the principles and guidelines related to an upskilling component on Open Science policy addressed to MS/AC, focused primarily on digital skills and including legal, ethical and IPR related issues, but also addressing soft capabilities needed such as science communication, public engagement, stakeholders' collaboration etc. MS/AC should adapt them to</p>

	<p>their related policies (open science/digital/education/research or any other) accordingly and in an integrated way, avoiding overlapping or fragmentation.</p> <p>2. MS/AC shall put in place measures in order to ensure that various digital ecosystem actors (organisations performing research, funders, public and private, industry) fully comply to any established open science/data upskilling policy, especially when research funding is requested, respecting IPR issues.</p>
Expected outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Guidance document: Principles and Guidelines for national digital upskilling component on Open Science ▪ MS/AC compliance measures for the alignment of all actors' initiatives on Open Science /Data upskilling
Stakeholders involved	EOSC, MS/AC governments
Shared costs & funding	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ESF+ and (National Operational) Programmes 2021-2027 2. Technical Support Instrument - TSI (Former Structural Reform Support Programmes - COM(2020) 409 final)

3.2.2 RECOMMENDATION 2. Promote education and training in Open Science Principles (e.g. FAIR & Open Data/Access) into EU policies and into the European institutional framework

RECOMMENDATION 2. Promote education and training in Open Science Principles (e.g. FAIR & Open Data/Access) into EU policies and into the European institutional framework	
	Thematic Area: Policy
Rationale	<p>The landscape report and the gap analysis indicated that <i>“there is not a concerted effort in skills and capacity development”</i> on European level. Furthermore, while, there is some conceptual knowledge on the different digital professional profiles for Open/Data Science (such as Data scientists, data stewards, data curators) there is <i>no clear definition nor recognition on the related profiles. This leads to some lack of clarity concerning the necessity for Open Science/Data principles’ training</i>, which is strengthened by the deficiency detected by the landscape report in the provision of relative <i>incentives into mobilizing upskilling in Open Science</i>.</p> <p>The issue of <i>motivation</i> is also an essential question that raised from the consultation process. These incentives could stem:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ either immediately from the obligations of a coherent institutional framework for Open Science that tackles upskilling, which is actually absent, constituting another major finding of Gap Analysis, ▪ or indirectly through some amendment in the rules set out in the financial instruments and funding programmes (such as ERASMUS+, Horizon Europe) concerning for example the expenses eligibility or the proposals evaluation criteria. <p>In addition, other motives could be the inclusion of digital training activities on Open Science in the EC related policy action plans or the integration of Open Science principles’ training in EC policy frameworks.</p>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	4.1 National policies and initiatives on open/data science
Suggested Actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EOSC may encourage Open Science Principles to be applied and included in the European Digital Education Content Framework, scheduled within the Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027, or develop a Digital Education Content Framework specific to open and FAIR data, that will reflect the need for the interoperability, certification, verification and transferability of content. 2. EOSC may propose to the EC a legislation framework on open science, similar to the Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive, with a statutory scheme on research data and related skills. 3. EOSC may provide advocacy support for the promotion of Open Science digital skills acquisition and development on EC and national level policies. In fact, EOSC may provide proposals (via drafting position papers, concept

	<p>notes, guidelines) to EC and MS/AC, concerning the establishment of incentives for boosting Open Science upskilling to be rolled out into national and EC policies and interventions, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ By making expenses for Open Science skills reinforcement, recognition and reward eligible for funding in research programs and financial instruments, or ▪ By requiring a certain level of Open Science digital skills as a prerequisite for researchers' overall professional advancement within EC funding schemes (such as forthcoming Horizon Europe, ERASMUS+) ▪ by integrating Open Science principles' training in all EU research related policies (such as ERA and HRS4R)
Expected Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Digital Education Content Framework specific to open and FAIR data (scheduled within the Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027) ▪ White Paper on a legislation framework on open science ▪ Proposals on incentives for boosting Open Science upskilling at European and MS/AC level
Stakeholders involved	EOSC, European Commission, Research Funders
Shared costs & funding	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ESF+ and (National Operational) Programmes 2021-2027 2. Horizon Europe 3. Technical Support Instrument – TSI (Former Structural Reform Support Programmes – COM(2020) 409 final) 4. ERASMUS+

3.2.3 RECOMMENDATION 3. Develop, consolidate, disseminate and mandate the use of high-quality, modular, tailor-made educational and training material for Open/Data Science (curricula, courses, on-line lessons)

RECOMMENDATION 3 Develop, consolidate, disseminate and mandate the use of high-quality, modular, tailor-made educational and training material for Open/Data Science (curricula, courses, on-line lessons)	
	Thematic Area: People & Actors
Rationale	<p>According to the landscape report and the GAP analysis, in the selected countries, there seems to be a <i>variety of academic courses related to Data Science and Engineering, Data Analysis, Data Mining, Digital Marketing and Data Science, Data Science for Business, Digital Transformation, Public Health Data Science, Big Data, Artificial Intelligence</i>. Most of them are addressed to post graduate students (MSc), however in some countries similar curricula are part of the undergraduate studies, mainly in the disciplines related to ICT. Specific modules are also embedded, as standalone courses, within curricula of several other disciplines. Many Universities offer the related MSc, undergraduate degrees, or courses, however the approach to the planning and the development of the related curricula, at national level and under a specific educational strategy, seems disparate. <i>Very few curricula related to EOSC on advanced, core expertise data skills for scientists were identified.</i></p> <p>More specific <i>skills development in Open Science practices</i> as part of university education or training <i>is regarded as a major factor towards capacity building and establishing a critical mass of professionals to serve the current demand</i>. The findings of the analysis, however, suggest that in the vast majority of cases the courses related to open science and open data practices are actually part of an ICT or business-related curriculum (spearheaded by courses related to data analytics and data science) and <i>not “fit for purpose” courses towards Open Science that actively focus for example on educating on and promoting FAIRness principles</i>. The emphasis on ICT related courses is on one hand encouraging, since several EOSC related skills are strongly empowered (as for example Data curation / stewardship, Research software development, ICT infrastructure operations), but on the other hand courses that would develop other skills for Open Science expected to be encountered in different disciplines (such as law, ethics, humanities) are seriously lacking (for example Intellectual Property Rights management of Open Data, Ethics of open data utilization in the private sector, etc.). Moreover, even though there are several well-established courses mainly at graduate level in most of the countries studied, a variable spectrum of availability depending on the country was observed and in any case these courses are quite few in absolute numbers. <i>Specific Open Science related courses are limited to few selected examples either interdisciplinary or domain-specific and form the exception rather than the rule</i>. An important aspect that differentiates the countries studied is the <i>availability of Open Science modules in environments close to academia and research, such as R&D Institutions, networks, scientific centres, scientific libraries</i> which serve as an alternative – but close to universities – source of digital upskilling.</p> <p>Regarding Lifelong Learning (LLL) related to digital skills, several initiatives have been identified with various scope and content for different target groups. Almost all countries exhibit formal or less formal systems for LLL, within the education and</p>

	VET sector, with modules related to digital skills, however the scoping differs according to policies' priorities and gaps to tackle in each country. Even though an important activity is undergoing in the related LLL policies, many of them financed by ESF, <i>little advanced training was identified to be targeting researchers.</i>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p>1.1 Education on EOSC knowledge fields</p> <p>1.2 Lifelong learning on EOSC knowledge fields and digital skills</p> <p>2.1 Higher education curriculum on digital skills on EOSC knowledge field aligned with industry demand</p> <p>2.2 Training of researcher in open science principles</p> <p>2.3 Lifelong learning and upskilling for citizens and researchers on EOSC knowledge field</p>
Suggested Actions	<p>1. MS/AC's relevant policy makers (such as Ministries of Education, Universities) should explore existing curricula of various programs on Open Science addressed to LLL, secondary and tertiary education, regarding digital skills for Open Science (such as FAIR and Open Data Management, Stewardship, Access, Dissemination & Sharing) tackling legal, ethical and research integrity aspects. Within this context, Universities, apart for sharing their expertise, could also develop MSc/BSc degrees in cutting edge technologies (such as AI, Cybersecurity) considering Open Science principles.</p> <p>With the aim to align existing educational and training material for Open/Data Science (curricula, courses, on-line lessons) to research and market demand via a system of skills 'intelligence', EOSC may host a multi-stakeholder Scientific Skills Committee to monitor and asses needs and methods for Open Science skills training and education, and to provide recommendations on the education content and scope. This Committee's work has to take into account the existing curricula at EU and national level, their potential adaptation to Open Science needs; the MS/ACs research and training infrastructures/platforms, the European market demand, the rapid changes in the digital technology, the capacity and the expertise of the educational and training ecosystem, and the best practices of innovative training.</p> <p>EOSC could support this Committee by conducting supportive studies, disseminating the recommendations of the Committee to the MS/AC's policy makers and providing them support on integrating these recommendations into MS/AC educational/training systems and research infrastructures.</p> <p>2. Universities could be motivated to share training material and being FAIR in its use. A rewarding system for the use of the existing material on open science could be set as an incentive by the funders to avoid n-plication and 'new' development. An initiative for Universities' inter-operability on training exchange may involve networks of Universities and of trainers.</p> <p>3. Universities could also be incentivised to develop tailored advanced courses on Open Science principles for researchers and data stewards and curators by capitalizing on their core research data expertise. To this direction, national initiatives in data carpentries' skills and professionalisation could be explored by EOSC in order to assess transferability and provide the curricula outline.</p> <p>4. EOSC should elaborate and disseminate a formal, coherent set of Implementation Guidelines for researchers and data stewards/curators at all</p>

	<p>levels on how to actually apply Open Science principles into their everyday practice and promote “learning by doing” concepts in all relevant institutions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Because trainings rely on many approaches, certification and standardisation of training is very important to have tangible outcomes; Moreover, certification is needed throughout the overall process: ‘developing/adapting’ curricula, preparing the training material, delivering training. EOSC may suggest the guiding principles for the certification of the above. 6. EOSC could launch a pilot initiative to investigate innovative training techniques and tools for research training infrastructure, to organise a pan European core network of data stewards and curators with the skills to work on these research infrastructures, and develop and deliver to them a respective training programme. 7. Following the recommendations of the Skills Agenda, EOSC may develop a mechanism encompassing ‘individual learning accounts’, supporting career paths of EOSC professionals and digitalise the process through the development of a digital platform. MS/AC should localise it and provide integrated and updated information at national level, with the aim to addressing existing Open Science individual training gaps. 8. Supporting the implementation of the Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027, EOSC could promote the understanding of open data and emerging technologies and their applications in education, by developing ethical guidelines on artificial intelligence (AI) and data usage in teaching and learning for EOSC actors, and by building on Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence. The guidelines can be accompanied by a training programme offered online or by the education and training network of MS/AC, which will be addressed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ to researchers and students focusing on the ethical aspects of AI, making sure to reach a target of 45% female participants in the training activities; ▪ to trainers and educators on communication skills and on how to conduct research in the frame of EOSC.
<p>Expected outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Open Science Curricula in secondary, tertiary education and LLL, MSc/BSc degrees in cutting edge technologies, tailored advanced courses on Open Science for researchers and data stewards ▪ Framework for a monitoring and needs’ assessment mechanism for Open Science digital upskilling- EOSC Scientific Skills Committee ▪ Implementation Guidelines for ‘individual learning accounts’ ▪ Pilot initiative to investigate innovative training techniques and tools ▪ Guidelines on artificial intelligence (AI) and data usage in teaching and learning for EOSC actors ▪ Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
<p>Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>EOSC, Ministries of Education, Universities, Training and LLL Actors</p>
<p>Shared costs & funding</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ESF+, ERDF and (National Operational) Programmes 2021-2027 2. Horizon Europe 3. ERASMUS+ 4. Technical Support Instrument – TSI (Former Structural Reform Support Programmes – COM(2020) 409 final)

3.2.4 RECOMMENDATION 4. Support researchers' career development rewarding open science practicing

RECOMMENDATION 4 Support researchers' career development rewarding open science practicing	
	Thematic Area: People & Actors
Rationale	<p>According to the landscape report and the GAP analysis, in the selected countries, there seems to be <i>no rewarding process for researchers' career advancement for open science practices</i>. Providing clear incentives and rewards to career researchers for adopting and practicing Open Science principles in their work constitutes an important motive towards pursuing improvement of their digital skills. Unfortunately, the current situation presents a significant gap in almost every country surveyed. In general, academic research is rewarded by the government or other R&D institutions where there is participation also from the private sector, for example in the form of grants or credits, however very few countries have established clear, specific incentives for complying with Open Science principles. Other countries are clearly planning specific award schemes based on Open Science related performance, but <i>most of the countries do not yet differentiate their rewards if Open Science research principles are followed</i>. That said, there are several "pilot" or individual initiatives undertaken in some countries that reward excellence in Open Science research.</p> <p>A formal process for career development for researchers provides constant motivation for excellence and thus opens up prospects for links with highly sought-after positions in Industry and facilitates professional work in Academia. Thus, the existence of such processes ensures a higher influx of potential Open Science practitioners. <i>Most countries have a very firm and developed process for the career advancement of researchers, usually under a formal legal framework. The development paths though are much more detailed and specific for an academic career than for public sector service or as gateways to the industry and the private sector and cannot thus be considered integrated into the ecosystem.</i> There are differences observed between the countries in terms of degree of awareness, transparency, performance assessment or administrative establishment of the processes. Examples of practices that are considered favourable to attracting new researchers are the civil servant status administered to researchers, existence of collective labour agreements with Universities and support of well-organized programs to offer related jobs. <i>There is however room for improvement in several countries, especially as it relates to advancement transparency and methods for rendering the academic career more attractive. What is also clearly missing is a set of guidelines or similar support measures to help policy makers develop and formalize clear career pathways that are custom designed to target researcher profiles aligned with Open Science.</i></p>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p>1.3 Recognition (evaluation and reward mechanisms) of EOSC professionals and researchers</p> <p>1.4 Professional digital career paths development</p> <p>3.2 Framework for lifelong learning pathways for different data/EOSC profiles</p>

Suggested Actions to be taken	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EOSC may landscape and analyse existing frameworks (research skills' taxonomy, guiding principles, governance schemes) for the development and establishment of Open Science profiles for EOSC research actors (such as researchers, data stewards and data curators), with the aim to identify the most appropriate (or a synthesis of them if more than one) to be promoted in the national mechanisms/systems. 2. Thereafter, with the aim to keep consistency across EU and promote diverse range of career directions, EOSC could provide guidelines to help national policy makers developing and formalising clear career pathways for EOSC research actors, encompassing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ rewarding mechanisms close to Open Science principles, eventually speculating on the inclusion of awarding FAIR practices with credits. These should be used to incentivise mostly students and early career researchers ▪ evidence-based monitoring mechanisms (including KPIs) for researchers' mobility follow-up through their career paths. <p>The DORA Declaration on research assessment should be considered within this career development guidelines.</p> 3. Taking into account these guidelines, MS/AC should provide incentives and support measures towards developing a career reward structure (capitalizing on the open science principles adoption) for all researchers, and particularly for Early Career Researchers. In addition, EOSC could also draft a white paper to EC based on these guidelines and the findings from their application, with a view to proceed with institutional provisions. 4. A broadly acceptable existing approach should be endorsed by MS/AC, for all the above, plus an implementation roadmap, provided by EOSC, taking no more than 2 years of implementation; Alignment needs to be undertaken at all levels and for all stakeholders, within the assessment and the evaluation of research, respecting national accreditation and research assessment and evaluation systems and taking into account initiatives and guidelines at EU level. EOSC should closely monitor this alignment through a relevant mechanism (<i>see also recommendation 11 for the maturity model</i>).
Expected Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Framework on Open Science profiles for EOSC research actors ▪ Guidelines for national career pathways for EOSC researchers (rewarding mechanism, evidence-based monitoring mechanism for researchers' mobility). EOSC related White Paper on regulatory provisions ▪ Incentives and support measures for rewarding researchers at MS/AC level ▪ Implementation roadmap for the MS/AC to follow
Stakeholders involved	EOSC, Ministries of Education/Research, Research Performing Organisations
Shared costs & funding	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ESF+ and (National Operational) Programmes 2021-2027 2. Horizon Europe 3. ERASMUS+

3.2.5 RECOMMENDATION 5. Promote credentials and qualification systems in regards to Open Science / Data skills for all

RECOMMENDATION 5 Promote credentials and qualification systems in regards to Open Science / Data skills for all	
	Thematic Area: People & Actors
Rationale	<p>Most countries endorse the DIGICOMP, and the EU framework, as the sound reference for the certification of digital skills and some of them have established National Qualifications Systems. MSc are certified level 6, whereas undergraduate studies level 5. Most Qualification Systems have as primary objective to raise the qualification levels of the active population in digital skills. ECDL is the most commonly used process for ICT skills certification. <i>No certification on advanced digital skills is identified; almost all qualification and certification systems are related to the LLL national policy.</i></p> <p>Also, regarding the standardisation of digital skills profiles, in almost all countries, <i>there is no evidence for the establishment of National Competences Framework related to digital skills. Only a few countries include in the competent framework data analyst and data science advanced skills professional profiles.</i></p>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p>1.6 Standardization of digital skills profiles</p> <p>1.7 Recognition and accreditation models of digital skills</p> <p>3.1 Quality assurance and certification framework for learning material for lifelong learning, ensuring up to date with technology and policy changes</p>
Suggested Actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC may provide advocacy for the update the European Digital Competence Framework with a view to including Open Science / Data related skills, minding for openness and FAIRness principles. Also, EOSC may establish a Working Group to explore: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the inclusion of micro-credentials promoted by the Digital Agenda; the development of modules of qualifications, in relation to learning outcomes, to flexibly update the content and to customise it to the needs of Open Science and advanced digital skills. EOSC may provide advocacy for the development of a European Digital Data Skills Certificate (EDSC), and contribution for considering Open Science principles inclusion, that may be recognised and accepted by governments, employers, researchers, data professionals, trainers and other stakeholders across Europe. This would allow Europeans to indicate their level of data competences, corresponding to the Digital Competence Framework proficiency levels. Also, EOSC may propose a validation framework of these outcomes leading to micro-credentials or partial qualifications for researchers and data professionals. EOSC may coordinate the transferability of related good practices and the alignment of certification at national level involving national bodies for certification, since the multi-disciplinary nature of data related occupations requires drawing from the expertise of each of these bodies.

	<p>Guidelines could be provided to MS/AC by EOSC to ensure minimal discrepancies in definitions of core knowledge, skills and behaviours and to avoid inconsistent adoption of good practices.</p> <p>4. EOSC may explore:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ a certification framework for trainers in digital professions, including soft and pedagogical skills; ▪ a certification framework for digital upskilling training environments for, considering Openness and FAIRness in training approaches and courses; <p>as a motivation means for the upskilling of researchers and data carpenters.</p>
Expected outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ European Digital Competence Framework including Open Science / Data related skills ▪ Working Group on micro-credentials and qualifications' modules ▪ European Digital Data Skills Certificate (EDSC) Framework ▪ Certification frameworks for trainers and training environments
Stakeholders involved	EOSC, Ministries of Education/Research, Competences Agencies, Accreditation Organisations
Shared costs & funding	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ESF+ 2. Horizon Europe

3.2.6 RECOMMENDATION 6. Ensure research integrity pertaining to Open Science data management & sharing

RECOMMENDATION 6 Ensure research integrity pertaining to Open Science data management & sharing	
	Thematic Area: Governance / Processes
Rationale	<p>The reproducibility and replicability of research results (research integrity) remains one of the most important aspects of the Scientific process and is constantly being criticized. One of the proposed solutions is to increase transparency in every step of the procedures involved, an aspect that Open Science is advocating at every level. It is therefore of paramount importance to have an uncontested view of what consists transparent and ethical scientific research according to OS principles for data management & sharing and to <i>train researches to practice it accordingly by enhancing their relevant core skills</i>, including data protection, IPR and selection of tools and methods for data anonymization.</p> <p>As was the case with most training initiatives in OS, the results from the Gap Analysis study indicate that <i>there seems to be a fragmentation regarding the establishment of a governance system for the upgrade of digital skills, which include not only core skills (such as Data Management, FAIR, Open Data, Open Access, Dissemination & Sharing), but also skills to handle legal, ethical and research integrity aspects</i>.</p> <p>Furthermore, with very few exceptions, in the countries that were studied there is not any legislative / regulatory framework in place to address the digital skills and competences building under a systematic and holistic approach, thus no indication of a quality framework regarding the practice and assessment of open science as regards research integrity.</p> <p>As a consequence, it becomes very difficult to a) recognize and accredit digital skills that support research integrity practice from EOSC professionals and researchers, b) measure impact and promote transparency throughout the community and c) systematically tackle the issue of Data Ethics when conducting Open Science research.</p>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p>1.3 Recognition (evaluation and reward mechanisms) of EOSC professionals and researchers</p> <p>1.7 Recognition and accreditation models of digital skills</p> <p>1.8 Quality assurance framework and certification mechanisms for trainers and trainees to ensure continuous improvement, accountability and sustainability, in alignment to the technology progress and any social or economic emergencies</p> <p>2.6 Recognition (evaluation and reward mechanisms) of EOSC researchers</p>
Suggested Actions	<p>1. EOSC may explore the establishment of a formal Scientific Board responsible for providing credentials on research integrity pertaining to the integration of Open Science principles, with emphasis on data management</p>

	<p>& sharing. EOSC may support the Board with the development guidelines¹ and an assessment framework with indicators for research performing organisations, aligned with relevant initiatives such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity² or the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.</p> <p>2. National Scientific Committees, which will be coordinated and monitored by the Board will be responsible for ensuring the research integrity as regards the integration to Open Science data management & sharing principles at MS/AC level. Research integrity boards, operating already at national level, could undertake this role (perhaps under a national coordination scheme). EOSC could launch an initiative to inform the national integrity boards on data ethics aspects and co-develop a certification framework, at the institutional level, for the corresponding responsible research/open science aspects;</p> <p>3. EOSC may provide advocacy, at EC level, for the establishment of an enabling environment for upskilling on research integrity practices, addressed mainly to Data Stewards and Researchers, through the drafting of a White Paper for the application of Open Data/Science ethics standards to every research organization and research project, respecting GDPR & IPR limitations.</p>
Expected Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EOSC Scientific Board ▪ OS Research Integrity Guidelines, Assessment Framework and Supporting Tools ▪ National Scientific Committees / Coordinated research integrity boards ▪ Data ethics certification framework ▪ White Paper for the application of Open Data/Science ethics standards
Stakeholders involved	EOSC, MS / AC governments, Institutions
Shared costs & Funding	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ESF+ and (National Operational) Programmes 2021-2027 2. Horizon Europe 3. ERASMUS+

¹ See for example the “Data Management Expert Guide” offered by the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (chapter on protection) to researchers practicing social sciences.

² The next version of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity will specifically address issues that arise from OS research and will emphasize the need for research integrity and proper ethical standards.

3.2.7 RECOMMENDATION 7. Promote & realise the development of Citizen Science

RECOMMENDATION 7 Promote and realise the development of Citizen Science	
	Thematic Area: People & Actors
Rationale	<p>Citizen engagement in research has been recently introduced as part of the new ERA by the European Commission and the European University Association calls on the Commission and EU member states to work with universities on providing the necessary support and developing adequate incentives and rewards to meaningfully engage in citizen science³.</p> <p>Raising awareness on EOSC principles and the benefits of Open Science in general is a major part of the communication strategy of the organization in order to increase OS visibility. Ordinary citizens who have an interest in one or more scientific fields need at the very least to be informed on OS principles in an understandable and attractive way, but with the ultimate objective to be an active part of OS.</p> <p>As a consequence, training of researchers should also include development of a larger spectrum of skills such as how to properly conduct scientific communication and public engagement activities, in order to foster an active, collaborative citizen science community which can ultimately impact the way research is conducted.</p> <p>Even though citizens might not be the top priority target audience for upskilling initiatives, nevertheless the larger their engagement in OS practices the more the expected benefits through diffusion of knowledge.</p> <p>Currently, there is <i>low awareness of the 'citizen science' (concept, even among the OS community and there are very few, disperse efforts towards citizen engagement and training researchers towards this goal, mainly in high visibility domains, such as healthcare.</i></p>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p>1.1 Education on EOSC knowledge fields</p> <p>2.3 Lifelong learning and upskilling for citizens and researchers on EOSC knowledge field</p> <p>3.4 Open learning and communication environments/platforms applying open science principles</p> <p>4.4 Linking universities, research, public domain and industry</p>
Suggested Actions	<p>1. EOSC should prepare a high-level document to describe the competencies and skills required for researchers to successfully engage with citizen science (including scientific communication, public speaking, social media, project management, project assessment, crowdsourcing, stakeholder management) and liaise with University associations to promote its deployment.</p>

³ <https://eua.eu/resources/publications/949:perspectives-on-the-new-european-research-area-from-the-university-sector.html>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. EOSC may promote a cultural change towards Open Science, through the organisation of (and participation in) various awareness raising and communication activities targeting mostly general public (including the Europe-wide citizen science campaigns foreseen in the new ERA). These activities shall aim at making Open Science popular not only in the research and academic environments, but also in the industry, public sector, education and the general population, by raising awareness on its major initiatives, results and benefits (personal and social) for all of its constituents (such as Open Science, Open Access, Open Data and FAIRness etc), including the promotion of any initiatives under an innovative concept of Citizen Science. 3. EOSC should fully align the above activities with the citizen science policies already set-in-place by the EC and take advantage of the forthcoming corresponding initiatives planned for Horizon Europe Program, by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Actively participating in the coordination mechanism of networks between citizen science initiatives and the “quadruple helix” stakeholders, ensuring that relative upskilling programs are in place; ▪ Closely collaborating with accelerators which will pilot a large number of “grassroots” actions for citizen science (to be funded by the Financial Support for Third Parties instrument) by providing guidelines and training resources to promote open science principles especially in data management & sharing; ▪ Providing formal opinion on required institutional changes for research funding and performing organizations (including Universities) to be able to a) directly conduct citizen science with OS principles and b) promote citizen science by working closely with interlocutors (such as civil society organizations). 4. EOSC could conceptualize and present to EC and MS/AC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ a European Open Science week for schools and Universities; ▪ a European Open Science day for citizens and general public; <p>as a permanent fixture in which skilled researchers can present to students and citizens the benefits of engaging in science as an “antidote” to scepticism and lack of trust in certain research areas.</p> 5. EOSC may facilitate the establishment of national points of contacts in Universities and their central coordination at EC level to offer support based on well recognized principles (such as the ones presented by the European Citizen Science Association and LERU) 6. Universities and Research performing institutions should establish formal collaboration with local communities and citizen (science) organizations to promote citizen science activities.
<p>Expected Outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High -level citizen science skills guide ▪ Awareness raising activities & events ▪ Opinion paper on proposed institutional changes to formalize citizen science in universities and research centers ▪ Conceptual framework & organizational model for OS week & day ▪ Organizational Committees at the above

Stakeholders involved	EOSC, MS / AC governments, Institutions, Research Communities
Shared Costs & Funding	Horizon Europe

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3.2.8 RECOMMENDATION 8. Foster an integrated at national level, robust, transparent, and participatory governance structure for digital skills on open science/access that supports the diversity of requirements across all disciplines, provides clear channels for feedback, and is compatible with other related initiatives at national and European level

RECOMMENDATION 8	Foster an integrated at national level, robust, transparent, and participatory governance structure for digital skills on open science/access that supports the diversity of requirements across all disciplines, provides clear channels for feedback, and is compatible with other related initiatives at national and European level.
	Thematic Area: Governance/ Processes
Rationale	<p>According to the landscape report, even though in all countries there are initiatives targeted to Open Science/Data digital upskilling and education, the governance model on the national level regarding the development and the establishment of an integral related policy is more or less fragmented. In particular, <i>many public organisations and/or ministries along with private sector entities, associations or collective bodies of research/academic/education/digital fields are being involved</i>, although without coordination or even clear and common objective. In fact, in most countries, there is <i>some lack of coordination and cooperation</i> among the national coalitions for digital skills and jobs and the research / academic organisations undertaking training activities on digital skills in Open/Data Science.</p> <p>Therefore, the issue at stake is the successful response of training programmes on Open Science/Data digital skills to the real and up to date market needs, in order to cover the increasing demand in professionals. Besides, <i>there are deficiencies into aligning the endeavors on Open/Data Science digital upskilling to related EC frameworks and action plans</i>, that generates a risk of exclusion from funding and policy development opportunities for EOSC.</p>
Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p>4.1 National policies and initiatives on open/data science</p> <p>4.2 National policies and initiatives on digital skills</p> <p>4.3 National policies and initiatives on emerging technologies (AI, HPC, Cybersecurity etc)</p> <p>4.4 Linking universities, research, public domain and industry</p>
Suggested Actions	<p>1. EOSC shall explore the setup of a Pact for Digital Skills referred in Skills Agenda (Action 1), specific for Data Science, for the MS/AC to sign, minding for addressing the legal, ethical and IPR aspects. This Pact should support national policy makers' collaboration in the fields of research/education/labour market, with the aim to mobilize them into</p>

	<p>adapting their related strategies accordingly (such as strategies on digital skills/open science/digital/education) and to improve the coherence among the policy design efforts on digital skills and the emerging market and research skills requirements.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. With the aim to integrate national endeavours on open science upskilling policy development/upgrade, MS/AC should establish a participatory governance model, involving all respective stakeholders and governmental policy makers, considering the various different disciplines, minding for achieving alignment to the fast-changing technology. 3. National Coalitions on Digital Skills and Jobs should act as ‘hubs’ for close collaboration with other existing networks for research and training (e.g., network of libraries, Institutes, etc.) for facilitating a streamlined approach to digital upskilling, including Open Science upskilling. EOSC should establish a liaison channel and participate with a representative in the National Coalitions for Digital Skills and Jobs. 4. EOSC should develop a human inter-operability model, in order to establish common interpretation of open science upskilling ecosystem, by people with different grounds and with the aim to improve understanding and collaboration across networked environments, and conceptualise a pan-European comprehensive governance and cooperation model.
<p>Expected outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pact for Digital Skills for data science ▪ National participatory governance schemes for Open Science upskilling policy ▪ Liaison channels with National Coalitions on Digital Skills & Jobs and other research & training networks ▪ Human inter-operability model
<p>Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>EOSC, National Coalitions on Digital Skills and Jobs</p>
<p>Shared costs & funding</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ESF+ 2. Horizon Europe

3.2.9 RECOMMENDATION 9. Bring academia, research and industry together for: (a) knowledge exchange to meet companies’ research and (b) innovation needs and students’ and researchers cross-disciplinary gain of experience. Develop a framework for co-development aiming at fostering “upward convergence” in competences needed related to Open Data/Open Science

<p>RECOMMENDATION 9 Bring academia, research and industry together for: (a) knowledge exchange to meet companies’ research and (b) innovation needs and students’ and researchers cross-disciplinary gain of experience. Develop a framework for co-development aiming at fostering “upward convergence” in competences needed related to Open Data/Open Science.</p>	
	<p>Thematic Area: Governance/ Processes</p>
<p>Rationale</p>	<p>The “<i>lack of interdisciplinarity, coordinated and coherent approaches to skills and competences building and for education and training provision</i>” along with the “<i>Fragmentation in training resources</i>” and the “<i>Lack of a clear definition of digital professional profiles; Data scientists, data stewards, data curators and research software engineers ... needed for the development of data-driven, data intensive science</i>” put in danger the timely development of enough highly skilled professionals in Data Science which is an undisputed necessity on European level as well as the controlled progress and exploitation of research and innovation outputs.</p> <p>Furthermore, this deficiency of effective coordination among public, research and business domains are a negative factor for the mobility of researchers and high qualified digital scientists from the research and academia environment to the business and industry world or even to the government working environment, and does not support knowledge sharing opportunities. Therefore, this fact creates an unfavourable although challenging environment for the development of the Digital Competence Centers, which in addition, face their correlation and cooperation with other Competence Centres or hubs which may have common ground and interests. In order to address these challenges, <i>there seems to be a necessity for the development of a framework for co-development aiming at fostering “upward convergence” in competences needed related to Open Data/Open Science.</i></p>
<p>Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training</p>	<p>1.5 EOSC professionals’ mobility to industry and public domain</p> <p>1.9 Digital Competence Centers, networks of experts or any other alliances (working on the co-development of common practices and tools, stimulating and promoting the mobility of students, digital professionals and domain experts, and creating mobility opportunities beyond EOSC such as industrial internships)</p> <p>4.4 Linking universities, research, public domain and industry</p>
<p>Suggested Actions</p>	<p>1. EOSC could actively support the harmonisation of Digital Competences Centres’ operation by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ performing landscape analysis and needs’ assessment for the digital upskilling targeted to Research and Industry, tackling the needs and/or

	<p>capitalizing on the related results of major innovation initiatives for digital upskilling and Open Science, led by MS/AC actors (research/public organisations and private companies), with the aim to refine accordingly the national Digital Competences Centres' scope and adjust its operation;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ drafting a coherent study, by integrating the findings of the above landscape analysis and needs' assessment and the related to skills findings of EOSC landscape study of European CoEs (Centres of Excellence) for HPC (High Performance Computing) in relation to the EOSC, carried out for the benefit of the EOSC, and then, ▪ providing opinions, at EU level, for the alignment and networking with similar types of Competence Centres/Hubs to establish world-class reference points for advanced digital training or formulation of innovative approaches (e.g., digital solutions, artificial intelligence) to tackle research openness and market needs. <p>2. EOSC could create Common Principles Guidelines on digital upskilling for the cooperation of Academia-Industry-Public Sector including the question of a certain share of a common training/knowledge content, focusing in domains such as AI, Cybersecurity, Open Science / Data.</p> <p>3. EOSC could provide advocacy for the inclusion of content material for Open Science digital skills and could become actively involved in the EU Digital Skills and Jobs Platform, which is an EC funded project currently under development⁴.</p>
Expected outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Landscape analysis and needs' assessment for the digital upskilling targeted to Research and Industry in the context of the national Digital Competences Centres' operation ▪ Guidelines for the alignment and networking of Competence Centres/Hubs including the CoEs for HPC to establish world-class reference points ▪ Common Principles Guidelines for the cross-sectoral/cross-disciplinary cooperation for Open Science skills in the Digital Competences Centres ▪ Position Paper for Open Science skills content inclusion in the EU Digital Skills and Jobs Platform
Stakeholders involved	<p>EOSC, European Commission, MS/AC governments,</p> <p>Institutions: universities and research performing organisations</p> <p>Research funders: the European Commission, national research funders, and other funders of research activity.</p> <p>Research communities: practitioners from all research fields, clustered around disciplinary interests, data types or cross-cutting grand challenges.</p> <p>Industry: Business Associations, SMEs, PPPs</p>
Shared costs & funding	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ESF+ and (National Operational) Programmes 2021-2027 2. Horizon Europe 3. ERASMUS+ 4. Private research funders

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/european-digital-skills-and-jobs-platform-project-team-starts-work>

3.2.10 RECOMMENDATION 10. Develop and enrich the EOSC technical training infrastructures with comprehensive learning environments and human support networks to be disseminated through the EOSC Knowledge / Education Hub

<p>RECOMMENDATION 10</p>	<p>Develop and enrich the EOSC technical training infrastructures with comprehensive learning environments and human support networks to be disseminated through the EOSC Knowledge / Education Hub</p>
	<p>Thematic Area: Technology / Infrastructure</p>
<p>Rationale</p>	<p>Education and training courses offered to researchers constitute one of the key factors to support digital up-skilling, they are not however by themselves adequate to assist them in practicing OS principles. Researchers need to be able to readily and reliably get support in several aspects related to OS practice, such as discovery of resources and access to available technical infrastructures, online educational content, domain experts, software to facilitate their work, methods to share data and results, guidelines to publish their work under open access policies, answers on IPR and ethical questions, etc. Most of these topics require skills development on the field (“on-the-job training”), rather than the ones acquired through classroom training and therefore researchers are in need of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ a systematic “human support network” to provide assistance and guidance (as a high layer of “infrastructure”) ▪ fit-for-purpose platforms and tools to readily provide up-to-date content and sharing / knowledge services, available through the EOSC knowledge hub ▪ reliable, interoperable and available technology infrastructures upon which data can be stored, searched, retrieved exchanged under FAIR principles and thus have their value fully realized. <p>To this end, the establishment of open, collaborative and coordinated learning environments, encompassing the above building blocks, to facilitate dissemination of Open Science principles and advancement of related digital skills is considered a key priority for EOSC.</p> <p>However, both the landscape report and the gap analysis identified that <i>there is a wide disparity between the different forms under which a “learning environment” is conceptualized or materialized in the various countries studied and that this is probably due to the fact that there is no clear definition of scope or a “blueprint” to be followed.</i></p> <p>There are several networks, resources and assets that could be considered as “local” learning environments (for example in universities, libraries or research institutions), however these are limited, scattered across the landscape and scarcely coordinated. As a consequence, their potential remains largely untapped and therefore the lack of consolidated resources results in little room for their expansion and increase in visibility.</p> <p>The situation is analogous as regards the research infrastructures, which are important to facilitate collaboration, data sharing, knowledge exchange, learning</p>

	<p>and access to other related value-added services for the community. Our study indicated that <i>considerable difference has been observed in the degree to which these infrastructures are available and utilized specifically for Open Science purposes.</i></p> <p>Finally, the following gaps have been also identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ many <i>different approaches to the planning and the development of content</i> that is available to researchers through the various platforms. ▪ <i>few coordinated entities or groups of stakeholders undertake the role of a central hub</i> to foster education and training initiatives specifically targeted towards researchers & Open Science.
<p>Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training</p>	<p>1.9 Digital competence centers, networks of experts or any other alliances (working on the co-development of common practices and tools, stimulating and promoting the mobility of students, digital professionals and domain experts, and creating mobility opportunities beyond EOSC such as industrial internships).</p> <p>2.5 Advanced learning environments on EOSC knowledge fields</p> <p>2.7 Networks of researchers and EOSC professionals in open science</p> <p>3.3 Training/Educational Repositories on EOSC knowledge filed as part of digital competence centers or universities entities</p> <p>3.4 Open learning and communication environments/platforms applying open science principles</p>
<p>Suggested Actions</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MS/AC need to foster the gradual development of integrated national innovative learning environments which incorporate on-line repositories/libraries and promote the co-development of supporting tools such as platforms, data testbeds, software for data creation, storage and sharing, etc. and build federated research data infrastructure (platforms, tools, repositories, etc.) at national level, linked to EOSC knowledge system. Respecting the EOSC Interoperability framework is a key factor for success and thus a mechanism to monitor implementation is also suggested (see also recommendation 11). EOSC should provide guidelines to MS/AC to ensure coordination and a uniform approach. 2. EOSC may explore the model of GAIA-X data infrastructure project in order to assess potential transferability into EOSC’s federated infrastructures and promote collaboration among different learning environments on data skills and relevant technologies. 3. MS/AC need to build-up an integrated communication and delivery platform with scientific libraries for the provision of digital upskilling services for EOSC professionals, with strong emphasis on skills required to design, develop, operate and support modern technical infrastructures suitable for research and OS (for example cloud services, scientific software development). LIBER can provide the requirements according to the outcomes of its WG on Skills and coordinate training on core and soft skills. The EOSC Hub is suggested as the single point of access (see also recommendation 11). 4. MS/AC should develop and communicate national support networks of open science specialists: professional support staff, core specialists, legal experts, etc to serve researchers in practice. EOSC can provide the guidelines for the requirements and deployment plans of such a network,

	<p>and develop and operate the liaison platform at EU level, taking into consideration the fact that support is crucial to institutions and research organisations that haven't got yet the "critical mass" found in larger institutions to correct imbalances. It is strongly recommended to capitalize on the existing OpenAIRE network and design initiatives to reinforce NOADS to act as local support networks.</p> <p>5. MS/AC should take all appropriate measures to ensure availability of research results through open publication environments, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Read & Publish contracts in the context of a dynamic scholarly publishing system; ▪ Trusted Open repositories; ▪ Open Communication Infrastructures (such as AmeliCA); ▪ Utilization of Open Research Europe platform; ▪ conclusion of national open access license agreements with publishers. EOSC can provide templates for the structure and content of these agreements.
<p>Expected Outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Interoperability compliance monitoring mechanism ▪ Guidelines for the implementation of national innovative learning environments ▪ Requirements for communication & delivery platform on training infrastructures ▪ Training courses ▪ Guidelines & Operational plans for Human Support Network ▪ Human Support Network (Enhanced OpenAIRE NOADS) ▪ Guidelines for utilization of open publication environments ▪ Templates for national open access license agreements.
<p>Stakeholders involved</p>	<p>MS/AC governments, EOSC-EOSC Association, Scientific Libraries - LIBER, Publishers, Data Service Providers, Research Communities</p>
<p>Shared Costs & Funding</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Horizon Europe 5. ESF+, ERDF and (National Operational) Programmes 2021-2027

3.2.11 RECOMMENDATION 11. Ensure EOSC's sustainability and active contribution to EU policies, through the development of an EOSC Leadership Program on digital skills

RECOMMENDATION 11. Ensure EOSC's sustainability and active contribution to EU policies, through the development of an EOSC Leadership Program on digital skills	
	Thematic Area: Policies
Rationale	<p>According to the landscape report and the GAP analysis, in the selected countries, there seems to be a <i>rather limited existence/ application of coordination and central governance mechanisms on digital skills and competences building and related training provision</i>. There is absence of a unified approach on how digital skills development and training provision coordination are performed regarding Open Science, while each country seems to adopt different approaches and techniques for digital skills and competences' interdisciplinarity leading to <i>significant asymmetries in different national approaches for open science and digital skills for the broader community</i> are assessed.</p> <p>Also, there seems to be a <i>fragmentation regarding the establishment of a governance system for the upgrade of digital skills</i>, regarding open science/data. The governance structure for the policy ownership is shared among the government, the universities, and the libraries whereas, in most countries the stewardship of the open science policy relies on national or research councils. In addition, it seems that <i>the institutionalization of open science does not keep pace with its development</i>.</p> <p>Finally, a series of additional gaps have been identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Absence of frameworks, guidelines and tools for the integration of EOSC principles into all relevant policies for digital upskilling, including research funding ▪ Absence of a coordination framework for EOSC principles' integration to digital upskilling-Absence of coordination mechanism for the creation, adaptation and consolidation of open science and digital skills policies and activities at national level ▪ Challenges in embedding digital skills components and priorities into the national policies ▪ Absence of solid governance scheme for digital skills development to national stakeholders ▪ Absence of mechanisms for supporting policy makers in evidence-based decision-making regarding effectiveness of upskilling policies and initiatives and ensuring alignment of policy decisions to Open Science principles ▪ Limited Open Science contribution to the knowledge system and lack of incentives for open research practices ▪ Deficiencies concerning spread awareness and cultural shift on Open Science principles being widely applied ▪ Challenges regarding the involvement of end-users, accessibility, inclusion and equity, ethics, data protection and privacy and security.

Associated SRIA Priority for Skills & Training	<p>4.1 National policies and initiatives on open/data science</p> <p>4.2 National policies and initiatives on digital skills</p> <p>4.3 National policies and initiatives on emerging technologies (AI, HPC, Cybersecurity etc)</p> <p>4.4 Linking universities, research, public domain and industry</p>
Suggested Actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. One of the primary tasks of the EOSC Association is to continuously develop the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). This, related to skills, could rely on the adoption of the life cycle approach for the update of the relevant SRIA thematic and on the assessment of its Intervention Logic. EOSC could initiate the relevant mechanism, though the periodic evaluation (DAC criteria) of the SRIA skills component. 2. EOSC Association could also develop an action plan for the establishment of formal collaboration schemes on researchers' and data science professionals' digital upskilling, considering Open Science principles, with national policy making entities: Ministries, Social partners, Industry Associations, to ensure integration of EOSC principles for digital upskilling at all levels; Partnerships, Consultations, MoUs, Collaboration Agreements, etc. can be used at national level. The action plan should include a sound governance scheme for digital skills development as a proposal to national stakeholders. The Action Plan needs to be as concise as possible with allocation of tasks to the relevant stakeholders and practical, with a horizon of 18 months for its implementation. It should be developed in levels, addressing the different stakeholders' required contribution. Due to the envisaged important effort for its implementation, and the complexity deriving from a demanding ecosystem, a provision for technical support should be explored. 3. EOSC Strategy Committee should implement and operate a maturity model for supporting the evidence-based appraisal and decision-making regarding effectiveness of Open Science digital upskilling policies and initiatives, at national level. Its objective relies on the monitoring and continuous improvement, with a unified approach, of the above policies and initiatives. This could be developed according to the principles of the capability maturity model, structured in 5 levels for processes: Initial, Repeatable, Defined, Managed and Optimised and with the view to the 4 dimensions: People, Policy, Governance, Technology. A network of EOSC trained experts could support the MS/AC appraisal and provide relevant recommendations. A self-assessment process could run at national level. 4. EOSC may develop and propose a composite indicator, or set of indicators, for Digital Skills in Open Science, for both researchers and data science professionals, linked to existing ranking systems on monitoring scoreboard, such as e-DESI. 5. EOSC Association could develop a knowledge sharing platform, within the Knowledge/Education Hub, for the support of MS/AC and Research Organisations in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the transferability of best practices on Open Science digital upskilling for researchers and science professionals and the coordination of any potential cross-border collaboration for it;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the development of reference material (e.g., data management plans, output management plans, IPR guides) as well as the development of reference Frameworks, Guidelines and Roadmaps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ to conclude Open Science related initiatives and practices on digital upskilling, and ○ to propose practical approaches for their implementation or integration to specific environments; ▪ the development of a shared and interoperable platform providing interdisciplinary services, as a single point of reference, for training content integration and sharing and needs specifications' development for tailoring generic training materials to discipline specificities and data carpentries related to open science, where applicable; ▪ the establishment of AI data spaces, for training facilitation; <p>An EOSC Scientific Committee could be established to provide support to the above, taking also into account the need for considering other existing initiatives in this ground and building upon them, when their added value is acknowledged;</p> <p>6. EOSC could introduce recognition and visibility initiatives, to promote digital upskilling on Open Science. They could involve:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ common action undertaken by different types of leading research associations in digital skills for open science, being assessed as a good practice; ▪ EOSC awareness and 'training by example' ambassadors' network comprised by highly specialised experts, mentors and digital "champions", following the concept of SRIA and Skills Agenda to inspire and motivate researchers and data science professionals to upskill in data management and sharing; ▪ EOSC 'Open Science Digital Skills Passport' for researchers and data science professionals; ▪ annual Open Science Digital Skills Awards (at EU level) for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ students, researchers and science professionals, applying advanced techniques, combined with Open Science principles, in data management and sharing; ○ initiatives undertaken by actors and associations, exhibiting innovation in the approach of digital upskilling for researchers and data science professionals.
<p>Expected outputs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Monitoring & Evaluation mechanism for SRIA update ▪ Action plan for the establishment of formal collaboration schemes on researchers' and data science professionals' digital upskilling with national policy making entities ▪ Maturity model for supporting the evidence-based appraisal and decision-making regarding effectiveness of Open Science digital upskilling policies and initiatives ▪ Composite indicator, or set of indicators, for Digital Skills in Open Science ▪ Knowledge sharing platform, within the Knowledge/Education Hub ▪ EOSC Scientific Committee

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognition and visibility initiatives
Stakeholders involved	EOSC, European Commission
Shared costs & funding	Horizon Europe

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